

THE RATIO CATEGORY AND ITS SEMANTIC FIELD IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: In addition to providing a general understanding of the verb group in English, this article also examines its ratio categories. Information about the use of verb ratios in sentences and their additions is also given and explained through examples. In addition, the use of the relative forms of the verb in English, h It is also mentioned that there is a distribution based on the meaning of the form.

Key words: verb ratios, semantics, language category, transitive verb, intransitive verb, passive, transformation

There are three main types of verbs in English. Each of them is very important as a grammatical tense, a modal expression, and as part of stable phrases and word combinations. English is an English verb used in English. It is "to have". The main feature of this verb is that it has a full meaning (semantic), auxiliary (together with semantics) or modal (related to actions, the possibility or necessity of its execution). A verb in English is a part of speech denoting an action or state of a person or object. In the indefinite form, next to the verb is the particle "to". Based on their structure, English verbs are divided into simple, derivative, complex and compound (phrasal).

Simple (usually short and from one root): work, play, eat.

Derivatives (they have suffixes and prefixes): replay, enrich, prepare.

Complex (consist of two small words that are written together): underline, overtake.

Compound (they are also called phrasal, consist of two words and are written separately): carry on, look after, put on.

By their role in the sentence, we can distinguish semantic verbs, auxiliary, modal and linking verbs. Semantic (independent) verbs have their own meaning, they denote a certain action or state: (He works as a teacher). Auxiliary verbs have lost their meaning and perform only grammatical functions. It is important to remember that auxiliary verbs in English (to be, to have, to do, shall, will) can also act as semantic ones. Impersonal forms of the verb-there are impersonal forms of the verb that are not conjugated by persons and are not used as a predicate: infinitive, gerund and participle. The infinitive names an action and always answers the question "what to do?". The formal sign of the infinitive is the particle to. It can be used in a sentence with different functions. Gerund is an impersonal form of a verb that is used as a noun in sentences and can perform various functions.

In sentences, verbs play the role of a verbal predicate or are part of a compound nominal predicate. It is thanks to the verb that we recognize the beginning, continuation, end of the action or the state of the object.

There are two basic ratios in English, and the doer of the action is possessive in the sentence Participial sentences (active voice) and the doer of the action are unknown or reduced to the

second level the rest (passive voice) are relative clauses. It is known that in passive cases, the doer is usually unknown or is reduced to the second level.

Example for comparison:

- Tom cleans the room every day. (Tom is the owner of the sentence and the executor of the action is clear)
- The room is cleaned every day. (owner of action unknown in the sentence.)

From the above example, it is known that in sentences in the passive voice, the executor of the action the main attention is paid to its implementation. All passive sentences must have the device "to be + V3(ed)". Here the verb "to be". Part that changes depending on the person and the time, and the form "V3 (ed)" is the invariable part.

1. English is taught all over the world.
2. Latin was taught at universities in the Middle Ages.
3. We will be taught Japanese next year.

In some of the activities, the sentences are from the definite ratio to the passive ratio examples of turning are given. For this purpose, the sentence in definite proportion must be able to meet the following conditions.

1. *The verb in the sentence must be transitive.*
2. *The sentence must have an object.*

You can find out whether a verb is transitive or intransitive from dictionaries. Transitive verbs requires a complement and is opposite [T], intransitive verbs do not require a complement and is opposite [I] is placed.

Examples of transitive verbs: to read, to bring, to kill, to tell...

Examples of intransitive verbs: to cry, to rain, to sleep, to nod off

The complement in the definite article replaces the possessive in the passive article. As mentioned above, if there is no complement in the definite article or the verb is intransitive, this sentence, it is not possible to form a negative proportion.

☑ It's raining. / ☑ He came.

In passive sentences, the subject or person receiving the action is the owner of the sentence since it was used, the executor of the action fell to the second level. The doer of the action we can use the word "by" to express who.

A: Tom watered the flowers

P: The flowers were watered by Tom.

This ending is used exclusively with regular English verbs. There are several spelling rules for adding it:

If the verb ends in "-e", just add the letter "-d" (invite - invited).

If the verb ends with a consonant preceded by a short stress (more often in very short monosyllabic words), the last letter is doubled (stop - stopped). The exception is the letter - x (mix - mixed). If it ends in "-l", then in British English we also double it (travel - travelled). If the verb ends in "-r" and the last syllable is stressed, then "r" is doubled (prefer - preferred). The final "-y" changes to "-i" + the ending "-ed" only if there was a consonant before it (study - studied), and if there was a vowel, nothing changes (play - played).

Irregular verbs have their own unique forms. Of course, they need to be learned by heart. But this can be done in different ways. Forms are not so unique if they are divided into groups. This division is different, you can independently distribute the verbs from the table in the way that is convenient for you. For example, there may be such groups:

Group 1: all forms are the same (cut - cut - cut, put - put - put);
Group 2: replacing the last "-d" with "-t" (send - sent - sent);
Group 3: adding "-t" in 2nd and 3rd form (burn - burnt - burnt);
Group 4: replacement of the root vowel with the sound - "e" (feel - felt - felt);
Group 5: change the ending to "-ought" (buy - bought - bought);
6th group: root "-o" in the 2nd form, and the suffix "-en" in the 3rd (choose - chose - chosen).
In the statement, we only add endings (-s for he/she/it in Present Simple, -ed for Past Simple).
In the negative and the question, we use the auxiliary verb do in its various forms (do/does for Present Simple, did for Past Simple), while removing the ending of the verb (-s/-ed). Here you need an auxiliary verb to be, to have, or will, which is used in all types of sentences. Both negation and questions are built using this verb. Auxiliary verbs, in turn, are also conjugated (to be: am / is / are, to have: had, has). The main verb acquires the ending of the third form (-ed) or the ending -ing and does not lose it in negatives and questions.

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